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BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D1.7 – Software Development Whitepaper

WP1: Code optimization & scaling

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Executive Summary

This document describes the major changes of the updated version of the scientific software development white paper published by the first BioExcel project. The whitepaper reflected the current state of software development of the BioExcel codes, as well as updates to reflect changes in software development standards. The updated white paper is available from <https://zenodo.org/record/6404474>

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1 Introduction

This document contains only a short description of the major changes of the updated whitepaper with respect to the paper published by the first BioExcel project. The white paper describes general recommendations for scientific software, as well as all details on the development processes for the codes involved in BioExcel2. We therefore restrict the text in this document to the minimum required. Since the publication of the first whitepaper, some development directions as well as practices have changed. The major changes are presented in the next section for GROMACS, HADDOCK, CPMD QM/MM and pmx. In BioExcel2 the GROMACS/CP2K QM/MM interface has been added. Its development status is described in the whitepaper available at <https://zenodo.org/record/6404474>, but there are no changes to report here.

2 Major changes with respect to the previous whitepaper

Here we present the major changes in software development for the BioExcel codes.

2.1 GROMACS

Major changes:

- Bumped the C++ standard requirement from C++11 to C++17, mainly for enabling new memory management functionality which allows replacing old, fragile construct by modern C++ standard library classes.
- Move code review, continuous integration testing and issue reporting to Gitlab. These used to be on three separate platforms with were run in house. Having these three critical infrastructures on a unified platform bring major improvements both for a user perspective as well as from an maintenance perspective. The build machines are still managed by GROMACS team, such that we can test on all relevant CPU and GPU architectures.
- New modules will require full test coverage. This will be verified by means of automated coder coverage testing.
- Moved user support from a mailing list to a Discourse forum on the BioExcel website bioexcel.eu. This unifies the support of GROMACS with the other BioExcel codes. Furthermore, this makes it significantly easier to find answers to questions. In particular users are presented questions with answers similar to a question they are about to post, with both leads to quicker answers for the user, as well as far less duplication of questions and therefore lowers the load on both the support staff as well as users searching for answers.

2.2 HADDOCK

Major changes:

- Development process details for HADDOCK:
 - Updated the description of HADDOCK development pipeline and added HADDOCK 3 , the new open and modular version developed under BioExcel2.
- Retirement/Deprecation
 - Updated policy plans and notification timelines.

- Code health (Release/Version control/Review/Bug Tracking/Testing/Style)
 - Added description of how releases are processed, how versioning, code review, bug tracking and code testing are done in the HADDOCK context, what style is used and incremented feature request pipeline description.
 - bug tracking and code testing is done in the HADDOCK context, what style is used and incremented feature request pipeline description.
- Development process details
 - no changes
- Integration approach
 - Updated description to account for HADDOCK3
- Code Scalability
 - New section: Demonstrate the strong scalability of HADDOCK
- Web Server Design
 - Added plans and concept for HADDOCK v2.5 server
- HADDOCK Virtual Research Environment
 - New section: Describe the concept and implementation plans for a new Virtual Research Environment for HADDOCK3 developed in collaboration with the Netherlands eScience Center
- Copyright and License
 - Extended to account for HADDOCK3

2.3 CPMD QM/MM

Development is continuing. There are no major changes in the development process.

2.4 GROMACS/CP2K QM/MM interface

This interface has been added in BioExcel2 and as such was not part of the original whitepaper. All content here is therefore new.

2.5 PMX

Major changes:

- Transition to Python3
- The main focus on supporting ligand alchemy and free energy calculation workflows
- Ask BioExcel Forum now used for the bug-reporting and feature requests
- The main repository for pmx moved to: <https://github.com/deGrootLab/pmx>